

Assessment of Awareness Level of Quantity Surveying Profession: A Case Study of Secondary School Students in Auchi, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research work examined the popularity and status of the Quantity Surveying profession among secondary school students in Auchi, Edo state. This paper reviewed the level of awareness of the profession by secondary school students, the factors that can militate against the selection of Quantity. The population of the study includes male and female secondary school students, the actual target population was the senior secondary school students. The data collected was then analyzed by using percentages, mean score, and mean item score. The conclusion was drawn that the study attempted to capture the mind of the secondary school student's perspective about the Quantity Surveying profession in Auchi as regards the level of awareness of the Quantity Surveying profession. Quantity Surveying as a profession and its duties are still not well known among the secondary school students and more needs to be done by the professional Quantity Surveyors and the professional body (NIQS) by embarking on awareness programmes and campaigns in the secondary schools, particularly to the students in the senior classes to intimate them of the functions of the profession, benefits of being a Quantity Surveyor and how Quantity Surveyors can contribute to the development of Nigeria. Exploration of career education, career assessment should be a positive endeavour for secondary school students in senior classes. A thoughtfully constructed career choice, career assessment, and career scope processes will provide a meaningful, productive, and satisfying hope for the student's awareness of the Quantity Surveying profession. A recommendation was drawn that career choice must be brought into a clearer focus, starting with students in elementary school and continuing beyond, career orientation should be built into the secondary school curriculum to enable the students to know the functions of the different professions that they are going for before leaving the school, adequate planning should be made to carry out career assessment interviews on the senior school students before choosing a career in order to determine the area of their interest, on performance, the Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors for that matter should aggressively pursue ongoing continuing professional development programmes through seminars, workshops, and refresher courses to bridge perceived knowledge gaps especially in engineering projects, to address the low level of public awareness of the Quantity Surveying profession.

Key words: Quantity surveying, Secondary school students, Auchi, Awareness

1. INTRODUCTION

The majority of Nigerians are not well informed about the services offered by Quantity Surveyors in Nigeria [1,2,3]. This lack of awareness has led to the execution of construction works without due consultation with the quantity surveyor who is well versed in the financial and legal aspects of construction. Consequently, exploitation of clients at this level by construction workers and subsequent project abandonment abound [4,5]. The quantity surveying profession at the national level is threatened as areas where we are supposed to be at the helm of affairs nationally are gradually being taken by opposition from allied professionals such as Accountants, Economist, Engineers, Architects, Lawyers, etc. This apathy leads to the exclusion of quantity surveyors in the mainstream of the procurement Act. The Quantity Surveying profession is one of the famous professions in the construction industry, unfortunately, this is not known among secondary school students in Etsako West Local Government, Auchi. The level of awareness of the quantity surveying profession by secondary school students in Etsako west local government area should be a serious concern to all quantity surveying stakeholders in Edo state. In spite of all the awareness programme conducted by the Nigerian Institute of

quantity surveyors (NIQS) in Edo state, the level of awareness of the quantity surveying profession among the secondary school students in Etsako West local government is not effective.

From the observation, the secondary school students in Etsako West local government are unaware of the quantity surveying profession, neither are they aware of their duties/responsibilities. [6,7] maintained that the profession must be promoted and marketed through advertising to dispel society's misconception about it, in the long run, the inability of quantity surveyors to create awareness among secondary school students and to know what quantity surveying is all about, the range of professional skills and services they can offer among secondary school students and the society at large. The researcher has decided to embark on this research to create awareness of the quantity surveying profession. Thereby seek maximum awareness of quantity surveying profession among secondary school students.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section treated in detail the Methodology to be used in gathering data, types of respondents to be involved, sampling techniques to be adopted, and the various scientific methods that will be used in the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the collected data.

2.1. Sampling frame

The adequacy of a sample is assessed by how well such sample represents the whole population of participants from which the sample is drawn. [8,9]. In probability sampling, the sampling frame is defined as the working universe or non-theoretical population, [10,11,12]. The sampling frame for this survey will be a target population of Three hundred and Five Secondary school students in twenty-five selected secondary schools in Etsako West L.G.A as shown in Table 1. The sample sizes for the survey research include Five Secondary School Students from each school out of the selected secondary school (Table 2).

Table 1 : Sampling frame of respondents

S/Nos.	Respondents	No. of Respondent
i.	Male Secondary School Students	125
ii.	Female Secondary School Students	180
	Total	305

Table 2: Sampling size of respondents

S/Nos.	Respondents	No. of Respondent
i.	Male Secondary School Students	44
ii.	Female Secondary School Students	81
	Total	125

Source: Field study, 2019

2.2. Sampling technique

In many studies, the entire population cannot be used. The use, therefore, arises for the selection of a subset of the population that is to be studied. The results emanating from the analyzed data are generalized to the entire population. If the results obtained from a subset are to be generalized to the population, then the subset should be a representative subset, or some members of the population are selected for the study through a method known as sampling, and the selected subset or members are called sample. For this research, purposive sampling of the participants in the selected area was conducted. The purposive sampling technique is a method of selection whereby there are no fixed means of selection of respondents but the administrator distributes the questionnaire at his/ her convenience or as come in contact [13,14,15]. The sample consists of students in different secondary schools in Auchi, Edo state.

2.3. Data collection instrument

The data collection instrument that was used in this research work is a questionnaire. The questionnaire is a document prepared by the researcher which lists series of questions to be answered by the respondents. The researcher prepared series of questions to be answered by the students based on the information needed for the study. The purpose of using a questionnaire is to elicit written responses from the respondents of the research through series of questions put together with their aims in mind [16, 17]. The questionnaires provide data that is easily quantified by the researcher and it is not time-consuming like other methods e.g. the interview etc. The structuring of the questionnaires is based on the set objectives so as to reach a reasonable conclusion.

2.4. Data collection

A well-structured questionnaire was used in accordance with the stated objectives of this research work. The questionnaire will be administered to the various categories of respondents within the senior secondary schools' students in Etsako West (Local Government Areas) L.G.A. This is done in order to capture the mind and know the level of awareness of the quantity surveying profession among the respondents [18,19]. The questionnaire was directly administered to the secondary school students i.e. personal distribution to the respondent shall be the means of administering the questionnaire.

2.5. Validity test

Validity is the extent to which an empirical measure adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration. According to Aje's study as cited by [20] recommends that questionnaire should be carried out and it should include different groups, such as colleagues and potential users of the data. In order to confirm that the data collected are comprehensive and also establish the most productive form of data analysis, the initial draft of the questionnaire was presented to the researcher's supervisor. The input generated from the data was used to refine the questionnaire before the general survey was carried out.

2.6. Data analysis

A simple descriptive analysis was adopted, where a number of well-structured questionnaires will be distributed among students in secondary schools. The descriptive statistical analysis which includes the use of the table, frequency, percentage, and means score with respective explanation is used. The responses of the respondents were collected compared, aggregated, and presented in a tabular form. Based on this, frequencies of occurrence were established and used for the analysis. [1] rating formula was used for degree of occurrence as shown in equation (1):

$$P (\%) = \frac{n \cdot 100}{N} \quad (1)$$

Where; P = Percentage; n = Value of the item; N = Total value of the item

Relative importance index techniques (RII) was adopted in this study within various groups (i.e. consultants or contractors), the five-point scale ranged from (1-5) was applied for each factor (2):

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{A \cdot N} \quad (2)$$

Where W is the weighting given to each factor by the respondents (Ranging from 1 to 4), A is the highest weight (i.e. 4 in this case), and N is the total number of respondents.

The RII value had a range from 1 to 5. The higher the value of RII, most predominant factors. The RII is used to rank (R) the influential factors militating the selection of Quantity Surveying as a profession. These rankings made it possible to cross-compare the relative importance of the factors as perceived by the two groups of respondents (i.e. Consultants and Contractors).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Survey responses

One hundred and twenty-five questionnaires were randomly administered in twenty-five secondary schools, and a total of one hundred and twenty-five responses, representing 100% effective response rate, the maximum responses from each sampling frame are shown in the Table 3.

Table 4 shows the factors militating against the selection of Quantity Surveying profession as a career by secondary school students as ranked by the respondents are: Lack of career counseling with a mean value of 4.38, followed by the Dominating of the construction industry by engineers with mean value 4.12, followed by the Corruption with mean value 3.68, followed by the Lack of involvement of engineering orientation of modern project trend with mean value 3.66, followed by the False opinion of the society about the profession 3.66. The finding agrees with the studies [21, 22, 23]. Likewise, the table also reveals the smaller number of registered Quantity Surveying firms with a mean value of 3.58, Young Age of the Profession with a mean value of 3.33, and Specialization on only building work with a mean value of 3.32. The Secondary school students have moderately sore the false opinion about the Quantity surveying profession, adoption of alternative procurement arrangement as the constraints to the awareness of the profession among them.

Table 3: Name of respondent schools

NAME OF SCHOOL	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Auchi Polytechnic Secondary School, Auchi	5	4.0
Word of Faith Secondary School, Auchi	5	4.0
Morning Star Group of School	5	4.0
Awa Hope Group of School	5	4.0
South Ibie Secondary School, Iyakpi	5	4.0
Great Nation Group of School	5	4.0
Ibienafe Secondary School, Ibienafe	5	4.0
Abundance Group of School	5	4.0
High Light Group of School, Ibie	5	4.0
Amina Foundation Group of School	5	4.0
Goodness International School	5	4.0
Dominion Group of School	5	4.0
Momodu College	5	4.0
Grace divine Group of School	5	4.0
Altazi Islamic Model College	5	4.0
Future Hope Group of School	5	4.0
Elite International Academy	5	4.0
Bright Star Group of School, Jattu	5	4.0
St. Joseph International School	5	4.0
St. Philip Secondary School	5	4.0
Brilliant Children Academy, Bawak	5	4.0
Divine Grace Group of School, Jattu	5	4.0
Al-Haqeeqah Academy, Jattu	5	4.0
Izharud-deen Muslim Secondary School, Jattu	5	4.0
TOTAL	125	100.0

Table 4: Factors militating against the selection of Quantity Surveying profession

Factors militating against the selection of QS profession	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Means Score	Rank
Lack of career counseling	95	-	21	-	9	125	4.38	1
Dominating of the construction industry by engineers	85	-	25	-	15	125	4.12	2
Corruption	61	-	45	-	19	125	3.68	3
False opinion of the society about the profession	67	-	32	-	26	125	3.66	4
Lack of involvement of engineering orientation of modern project trend	70	-	26	-	29	125	3.66	4
Less number of registered quantity surveying firms	72	-	17	-	36	125	3.58	6
Young age of the profession	58	-	30	-	37	125	3.33	7

3.3. Factors that influence student interest in the selection of Quantity Surveying

Table 5 shows the result of the assessment made by the respondent on the factors that can influence student interest in the selection of Quantity Surveying (QS) as a profession. The factors as ranked by the respondents are: Interest in construction with mean values 4.54 as the first, followed by Personal innovation with a mean value of 4.50 as second, followed by Early school counseling with a mean score of 4.26 as the third, followed by Parental influence with mean value 4.23 as the fourth, followed by a Role model and mentor with mean value 4.17 as the fifth also the use of ICT in the profession, Publicity, Potential job placement, Media coverage, Family businesses and The School policy with mean

value 4.01, 3.91, 3.88, 3.78, 3.72 and 3.72 are averagely rated. Likewise, Status and prestige were the least ranked with a mean score of 3.61.

Table 5: Factors that influence student interest in the selection of quantity surveying as a profession

Factors that can influence student interest in the selection of QS as a profession	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Means Score	Rank
Interest in construction	105	-	11	-	9	125	4.54	1
Personal innovation	104	-	11	-	10	125	4.50	2
Early school counseling	92	-	20	-	13	125	4.26	3
Parental influence	90	-	22	-	13	125	4.23	4
Role model and mentor	89	-	20	-	16	125	4.17	5
The use of ICT in the profession	81	-	26	-	18	125	4.01	6
Publicity	76	-	30	-	19	125	3.91	7
Potential job placement	80	-	20	-	25	125	3.88	8
Media coverage	72	-	30	-	23	125	3.78	9
Family businesses	60	-	50	-	15	125	3.72	10
The school policy	61	-	48	-	16	125	3.72	10
Status and prestige	70	-	23	-	32	125	3.61	12

3.4 .Ways of improving the level of awareness of Quantity Surveying profession

Table 6 shows the results of the ways of improving the level of awareness of the quantity surveying profession among secondary school students. The analysis shows that Secondary school students have a very high belief that by making the function of QS known to the students their level of awareness about the profession will increase. This is arrived at because it happened to be the factor with the highest mean value of 4.62. The finding show high similarity with the studies [24, 25, 26]. The respondents have moderately scored the extents at which these factors: By making quantity surveying textbooks available in secondary schools libraries, by organizing career choice talk where quantity surveying will be the main subject of discussion, By improving the number of quantity surveyors in government work, and By organizing quiz competition annually in secondary schools in the name of the quantity surveying professional body. The respondent's response to the factor that their level of awareness can be influenced by adopting the strong interest inventory was very poor because this happens to be with the lowest mean value of 3.27.

Table 5: Ways of improving the level of awareness of Quantity Surveying profession among secondary school students

Ways of improving the level of awareness of QS profession among Secondary School Students	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Means Score	Rank
By making the function of the profession known to the students	106	6	5	-	8	125	4.62	1
By making quantity surveying textbooks available in secondary schools library	80	20	14	4	7	125	4.30	2
By organizing career choice talk where quantity surveying will be the main subject of discussion	76	26	9	4	10	125	4.23	3
By improving the number of quantity surveyors in government work.	57	42	10	11	5	125	4.06	4
By organizing quiz competition annually in secondary schools in the name of the quantity surveying professional body	62	27	18	12	6	125	4.02	5
Through teachers influence	62	22	21	11	9	125	3.94	6
Frequent publication of the profession activities	53	28	24	11	9	125	3.84	7
Through career assessments	51	32	22	10	10	125	3.83	8
By organizing a career development talk channeled towards quantity surveying profession	53	21	18	14	19	125	3.60	9
Through the process of career scope assessment	49	24	23	10	19	125	3.59	10
By increasing the number of students that study the course in higher institutions.	50	20	24	15	16	125	3.58	11

By carrying out career assessment interview	49	20	21	17	18	125	3.52	12
By introducing a career cluster that focuses on Quantity Surveying profession	42	25	17	16	25	125	3.34	13
By publicizing the profession through fliers that states the functions and other importance of the profession	40	20	27	19	19	125	3.34	13
By adopting the strong interest inventory	40	18	25	20	22	125	3.27	15

4. CONCLUSION

The study to assessed captured the awareness of the secondary school student perception of the Quantity Surveying profession in Auchi as regards the level of awareness of the Quantity Surveying profession. It is obvious that Quantity Surveying as a profession and its services is still not well known among the secondary school students and more needs to be done by the professional Quantity Surveyors and the professional body (NIQS) by embarking on awareness programmes and campaigns in the secondary schools, particularly to the students in the senior classes to intimate them with the functions of the profession, benefits of being a Quantity Surveyor and how Quantity Surveyors can contribute to the development of Nigeria. Exploration of career education, career assessment should be a positive endeavour for secondary school students in senior classes. A thoughtfully constructed career choice, career assessment, and career scope processes will provide a meaningful, productive, and satisfying hope of the student awareness of the Quantity Surveying profession.

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